

Supplemental Table 1: Different abiotic, chemical and molecular agents that evoke priming-induced abiotic stress response.

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
Abiotic agents					
Heat	Heat	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- 36/32°C(day/night)/48h T- 36/32°C(day/night)/7d R- from 5 leaf stage to 50% of the primary inflorescence was visible	Increased number of stomata	Mendanha <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Heat	Heat	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	P ₁ - 37°C/60min-R(90min)-P ₂ - 44°C/45min T- 44°C/90min R- 2d	Chromatin protein BRU1 is required for sustained transcriptional induction of <i>HSA32</i>	Brzezinka <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Heat	Heat	<i>Rhododendron hainanense</i>	P- 37°C/60min T- 42/35°C(day/night)/7d R- 2d	Improved photosynthetic rate and membrane stability, sustained accumulation of Chloroplast-localized	Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2020

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
				HSPs, RCA1, CPN60 β and pTAC5	
Heat	Salinity	<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	P- 45°C/30min T- 200mM NaCl/1h R- None	Induced <i>Cu/Zn-SOD</i> , <i>HvCAT2</i> and <i>HvAPX</i> transcription	Faralli <i>et al.</i> , 2015
Heat	Salt and drought	<i>Brassica campestris</i>	P- 42°C/5h/dark T- 150mM NaCl/20% PEG 6000/48h R- 25°C/6h/dark	Positively modulated the activities of APX, DHAR, GR, GST, GPX, CAT, Gly I, Gly II and maintained lower levels of GSSG, H ₂ O ₂ and MDA	Hossain <i>et al.</i> , 2013
Drought	Drought	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- 5% PEG/6h T- 5% PEG/24h R- 6d	Increased levels of protective proline and glycine betaine, promoted biomass accumulation and root growth	Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2021
Drought	Drought	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- Withheld from watering/7d (10d after anthesis stage)	Lower levels of H ₂ O ₂ and MDA, higher	Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2018

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
			T- SRWC decreased to 40% (10d after anthesis stage) R- 1-3 generations	contents of proline and glycine betaine, induced activities of P5CS1 and BADH	
Drought	Heat	<i>Festuca arundinacea</i> <i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- Soil volumetric water content decreased to 10%/10µM fluridone spray T- 38/33°C(day/night)/25d R- None P- SRWC decreased to 35-40%/5-7d T- 35/28°C(day/night)/until maturity R- 6 leaf stage to grain filling stage	Up-regulation of <i>CDPK3</i> , <i>MPK3</i> , <i>DREB2A</i> , <i>AREB3</i> , <i>MYB2</i> , <i>MYC4</i> , <i>HSFA2</i> , <i>HSP18</i> and <i>HSP70</i> Increased ABA	Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2019, Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2015
Drought	Cold	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- Volumetric soil water content decreased to 18.8%/21d T- 4/2°C(day/night)/2d	Higher leaf RWC, higher ABA and lower H ₂ O ₂ concentration, induced CAT and	Li <i>et al.</i> , 2015

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			R- 7d	APX activity, greater photosynthetic rate	
Drought	Salt	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- 1.5%(w/v) CaCl ₂ solution/12h (seeds collected from drought treated plants) Seed priming T- 100mM NaCl/9d R- till seed germination	Improved leaf area, water relations, increased grain yield, leaf proline and glycine betaine content, decreased concentration of MDA and Na ⁺	Tabassum <i>et al.</i> , 2017
Cold	Cold and freezing	<i>Triticum aestivum</i> <hr/> <i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	P- 10/4°C(day/night)/7d T- 2/0°C(day/night) R- 14d/sprayed 1mM melatonin (3 times) <hr/> P- 6°C/2°C(day/night) /sprayed 100mM SA(12h interval)/2d T- 2°C/0°C(day/night)/1 st day/- 2°C/- 4°C(day/night)/2 nd day R- 8d	Increased photosynthetic rate, stomatal conductance, membrane stability index, induced SOD, CAT and APX activity <hr/> Induced expression of <i>WRKY19</i> , <i>HSF3</i> , <i>AOX1a</i> , <i>HSP70</i> contributed to increase in antioxidant capacity and protection of	Sun <i>et al.</i> , 2018, Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2020, Xing and Rajashekar, 2001, Zhao <i>et al.</i> , 2009

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				photosystem and decreased malonaldehyde content, superoxide radical production	
Cold	Salt	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	P- 4°C for 6 h T- 150mM NaCl/7d R- None	Ion homeostasis and induced expression of photosystem related genes	Fan <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Cold	Heat	<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	P- 0°C/1-4d T- 35°C/until germination R- None	Increased activity of SOD, APX, CAT and GR	Mei and Song, 2010
Cold	Drought	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>	P- Seeds were soaked in 0.01mM SA solution after incubated at 25°C for 24h/7°C for 24h - Seed priming T- Mannitol treatment -0.3, -0.6, -1.2 MPa R- None	Induced proline accumulation	Yamamoto <i>et al.</i> , 2014

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
Salt	Salt	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	P- KNO ₃ solution (-1.0 MPa)/1d/30°C T- 5-, 10-, 15-, 20- and 25dS/m NaCl/40d R- None	Promoted K ⁺ and Ca ²⁺ accumulation and induced osmoregulation by the accumulation of proline	Bajehbaj, 2010
Salt	Cold	<i>Cucumis melo</i>	P- 2-3% solutions of KH ₂ PO ₄ + KNO ₃ (1-5 days) - Seed priming T- 10°C-16°C during germination R- Seed drying (28°C)	Not mentioned (Faster seed germination)	Nerson and Govers, 1986
Chemical & Molecular agents					
Thiamethoxam	Drought	<i>Glycine max</i>	P- 83mL/100 kg of seed-Seed priming T- Drought stress applied at the reproductive stage (gradual reduction of soil water content) R- till vegetative stage	Altered expression of plant defense and stress responsive genes	Stamm <i>et al.</i> , 2014

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
Protein hydrolysates (PH)	Salt	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	P- 0.1µl/ml of PH/3d/4°C - Seed priming T- 150mM NaCl/2d R- 3d	Reduced oxidative damage induced by the stress, regulating the crosstalk between different plant hormones	Sorrentino <i>et al.</i> , 2021
Clothianidin & Imidacloprid	Drought	<i>Saccharum spp</i> , <i>Nicotiana tabacum</i> , <i>Capsicum annuum</i>	P- 0.0151g/vase Clothianidin, 0.0120g/pot Imidacloprid, T- available water capacity 20%/32d R- 88d	Induction of SA response	Endres <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Ford <i>et al.</i> , 2010, Kerchev <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Paclobutrazol	Drought	<i>Eleusine coracana</i>	P- 100µM Paclobutrazol/6 times with 2d interval T- 200-, 400- and 600mM Mannitol R- None	Increased lodging tolerance by decreasing plant height	Plaza-Wüthrich <i>et al.</i> , 2016
Sodium nitroprusside (SNP)	Salt	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i>	P- 200µM SNP + 5mM H ₂ O ₂ T- 50mM NaCl R- 6d	Increased height and decreased MDA content	Gohari <i>et al.</i> , 2020

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SNP	Heat	<i>Zea mays</i>	P- 50-400µM SNP/6h T- 48°C/18h R- None	Increased activities of SOD and CAT, maintained Higher RWC.	Li <i>et al.</i> , 2013
SNP	Drought	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- 125µM SNP/8h - Seed priming T- 50% water holding capacity R- None	Upregulated antioxidant and hydrolytic enzymes with an increased level of osmoprotectants	Hameed <i>et al.</i> , 2021
H ₂ O ₂	Cold and Salt	<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> <i>Ocimum basilicum</i>	P- 0.1mM H ₂ O ₂ /4h/27°C/dark T- 4°C/7d R- 27°C/12h P- 5mM H ₂ O ₂ + 200µM SNP T- 50mM NaCl R- 6d	Induced mitochondrial CAT3 isozyme transcription and increased activity of CAT3 and POX Decreased MDA content	Prasad <i>et al.</i> , 1994, Gohari <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Polyamines	Salt	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	P- 1mM Putrescine T- 100mM NaCl/5d or 12d	Increased activity of ODC, ADC, DAO and PAO	Quinet <i>et al.</i> , 2010

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			R- None		
Benzyl Aminopurine (BAP)	Salt	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- 5mg/L BAP/12h T- 10dS/m electrical conductivity of NaCl R- None	Increased contents of chlorophyll, total phenolics, total soluble sugars and proteins, induced α -amylase activity, increased tissue K^+ ion and decreased tissue Na^+ ion contents	Bajwa <i>et al.</i> , 2018
Allantoin	Salt	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	P- 0.1mM & 1mM Allantoin T- 100mM NaCl R- None	Altered expression of antioxidant encoding genes, induced expression of <i>SOS1</i> and <i>RCD</i> (oxidative stress tolerance genes)	Irani and Todd, 2018
$CaCl_2$	Flooding	<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>	P- 60-, 120- and 180kg/ha $CaCl_2$ T- 100% water holding capacity/2d R- None	Increased contents of APX, SOD, GR, MDA, reduced GSH, total and reduced ascorbate	Lin <i>et al.</i> , 2008
Triadimefon	Salt	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	P- 5mg/L Triadimefon/12h	Increased activity of antioxidant enzymes	Jaleel <i>et al.</i> , 2008

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
			T- 40mM NaCl during seed germination R- None	like SOD, CAT, POX and PPO	
Kresoxim-methyl (KM)	Salt and Drought	<i>Medicago truncatula</i>	P- 10 ⁻⁸ M KM spray T- 200mM NaCl/48h withheld water/9d R- None	Increased stomatal conductance and proline content, decreased H ₂ O ₂ and MDA content, lowered NR activity and NO content	Filippou <i>et al.</i> , 2016
5-aminolevulinic acid (ALA)	Chilling	<i>Capsicum annuum</i>	P- 50ppm ALA (seed soaking and foliar spray on 30d old plants) T- 3 ± 0.5°C/48 h R- 3d	Enhanced plant biomass, increased chlorophyll, sucrose, and proline contents, increased RWC, stomatal conductance and SOD enzyme activity and reduced membrane permeability	Korkmaz <i>et al.</i> , 2010

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
Sodium hydrosulfide (NaHS)	Heat and Drought	<i>Fragaria ananassa</i>	P- 100mM NaHS/2d T- 42°C/8h R- None	Promoted the production of HSPs and antioxidants	Christou <i>et al.</i> , 2014, Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2010
		<i>Glycine max</i>	P- 0.05 and 0.1mmol/L NaHS (H ₂ S donor)/4d with 7d interval in between T- withheld watering/21d R- None	Increased chlorophyll content, higher activity of SOD, CAT and lower activity of lipoxygenases, decreased accumulation of MDA, H ₂ O ₂ , and superoxide anion	
Ketoconazole (KCZ)	Drought	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	P- 15mg/L KCZ (30d after sowing) T- no irrigation for 20d R- None	Increased production of alkaloid Ajmalicine and antioxidant potential	Jaleel <i>et al.</i> , 2007

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
NOSH-aspirin	Drought	<i>Medicago sativa</i>	P- 100µM NOSH- aspirin (foliar spray) T- withholding water for 6d R- None	Attenuation of cellular damage, modified reactive-oxygen and nitrogen-species signaling and metabolism, altered lipid peroxidation and proline accumulation	Antoniou <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Nitric oxide	Salt and Heat	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	P- 1/10mM SNP (NO donor)/2d T- 100mM NaCl/8d 50°C/5h R- None	Higher quantum yield for photosystem II, induced expression of genes encoding for <i>sucrose-phosphate synthase</i> , <i>P5CS</i> , and <i>small HSP26</i>	Uchida <i>et al.</i> , 2002
Melatonin	Low temperature, Heat and Salt	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i> <i>Triticum aestivum</i> <i>Medicago sativa</i>	P- 100µM Melatonin spray T- 15/6°C(day/night)/3d R- 25/15°C(day/night)/3d P-80ml of 100µM Melatonin/7d (foliar spray) T- 42°C/6h	Increased electron transfer rate and quantum yield of PSI and PSII Boosted antioxidant defense system and regulating the	Yang <i>et al.</i> , 2018, Buttar <i>et al.</i> , 2020, Yu <i>et al.</i> , 2021

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
			R- 7d P- 150µM Melatonin - Seed priming T- 250mM NaCl R- None	transcription of stress-responsive genes. Increased antioxidant enzyme activity and proline levels	
Ascorbate	Salt	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- 100mg/L ascorbic acid T- 150mM NaCl R- None	Higher photosynthetic capacity, and accumulation of K ⁺ and Ca ²⁺ in the leaves, induced CAT activity	Khan and Ashraf, 2008
Glutathione (GSH)	Salt	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	P- 5mmol/L GSH spray T- 100mmol/L NaCl R- None	Increased photosynthetic efficiency, decreased accumulation of H ₂ O ₂ and MDA, induced activity of SOD, CAT, POD	Yan <i>et al.</i> , 2018

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
Methylglyoxal	Cold	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- 5-,10- or 25mM Methylglyoxal/15m/ 2 times with 2d interval T- -3°C, -5°C and -7°C/1 or 2d R- 2d	Improved chlorophyll content and photosynthetic activity, increased transcript levels of GST and omega-3 fatty acid desaturases, increased activity of AKRs, Gly	Majláth <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Acibenzolar-S-methyl (fungicide)	Heat and Drought	<i>Agrostis stolonifera</i>	P- 7.37mg ASM/m ² foliar spray T- 35/30°C(day/night)/56d Soil volumetric water content 6%/14d R- 16d	Increased chlorophyll content, RWC, increased protein content of ATP synthase, HSP20, PR3, Rubisco and dehydrin	Jespersen <i>et al.</i> , 2017
Glycine betaine (GB)	Salt	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>	P- 5 and 10 mM/I GB/3 times with 2 weeks of interval (foliar spray) T- 50mM NaCl R- None	Increased levels of soluble sugars	Manaf, 2016

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Proline	Salt	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	P- 5mM Proline/sprayed twice a day T- 150 and 300mM NaCl R- None	Reduced oxidative damage, increased antioxidant defense system	Hasanuzzaman <i>et al.</i> , 2014
Trehalose	Salt and Drought	<i>Oryza sativa</i> , <i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	P- 10mM Trehalose T- 100mM NaCl/6d R- None	Reduced Na ⁺ /K ⁺ ratio, increased activity of APX and transcripts of antioxidant enzyme genes	Nounjan <i>et al.</i> , 2012
GABA	Freezing	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	P- 100-, 250-, 500- and 750μmol/L GABA T- 2±0.5°C/48 h R- 3d	Increased contents of sugars and proline	Malekzadeh <i>et al.</i> , 2014
BABA	Drought	<i>Brassica napus</i>	P- 300μM BABA T- withheld water/4d R- 1d	Increased ascorbate, anthocyanin, flavonoid content and SOD, APX, POD, CAT activity,	Rajaei and Mohamadi, 2013

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
				decreased DHA content	
Spermidine (Spd) and Spermine (Spm)	Salt	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	P- 1mM Spd or Spm/6h T- 150mM NaCl R- None	Improved photosynthetic efficiency, prevented the leakage of electrolytes and amino acids and regulation of chloroplast-encoded genes	Chattopadhyaya <i>et al.</i> , 2002
Vitamin K ₃	Chilling and Salt	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	P- 0.1mM menadione /4h/27°C/dark T- 4°C/7d R- 27°C/12h P- 2-, 20- and 40mM Menadione sodium bisulfite /2d/4°C - Seed priming T- 50mM NaCl/7 and 14d R- 21d	Increased survival and growth, upregulation of <i>CAT3</i> transcript Proline accumulation, induction of <i>ZAT10,11,12</i> genes	Prasad <i>et al.</i> , 1994, Jiménez-Arias <i>et al.</i> , 2015

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
Copper nanoparticles (Cu NPs)	Salt stress	<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	P- 250mg/L Cu NPs T- 50mM NaCl R- None	Improved phenol content, vitamin C, GSH, increased activity of PAL, APX, GPX, SOD, and CAT enzymes	Pérez-Labrada <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Brassinolide	Salt and Heat	<i>Oryza sativa</i> <i>Vigna sinensis</i>	P- 0.005mg/L Brassinolide/7 times with 2d interval T- 38°C/30°C(day/night)/3d R- 15d P- 0.05ppm brassinolide (foliar spray 2 times) T- 25-, 50-, 100-, and 150mM NaCl R- None	Increased chlorophyll content and activities of POD and SOD enzymes, reduced MDA levels and electrolyte leakage Increased lipid peroxidation and content of ascorbic acid, tocopherol, and GSH	Cao and Hua, 2008, El-Mashad and Mohammed, 2012
Indole acetic acid (IAA)	Drought	<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	P- 15 and 30mg/L IAA spray T- withheld water/5d	Increased growth, Photosynthetic efficiency and water use efficiency	Ashraf <i>et al.</i> , 2006

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
			R- None		
Salicylic acid	Heat and High light	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- 0.1-, 0.3- and 0.5mM SA foliar spray T- 39 ± 2°C/ 1,800µmol photon/m ² s of PPF/2h R- 3d	Improved photosynthetic rate and chlorophyll content, increased activity of antioxidant enzymes, protection of PSII complex through enhanced <i>psbA</i> gene transcription	Wang <i>et al.</i> , 2014
Absciscic acid	Salt	<i>Vicia faba</i>	P- 10µM ABA/24h T- 50mM NaCl/8d R- 15d	Increased root and shoot dry matter, improved photosynthesis, and inhibited terminal wilting of plants	Sagervanshi <i>et al.</i> , 2021
Jasmonic acid	Salt	<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	P- 2mM JA foliar spray/2 times at 2-day intervals T- 150mM NaCl R- 3d	Increased transcript levels and activities of SOD, POD, CAT and APX and contents of GSH, Chlorophyll b and	Qiu <i>et al.</i> , 2014

Priming agent	Abiotic (Triggering) stress	Plant species	Intensity /Duration/ Recovery	Mechanism of action	Reference(s)
				carotenoid, decreased concentration of MDA and H ₂ O ₂ , the production rate of O ₂ ⁻	

P refers to Priming stimulus (Mild stress/signaling molecule which initiates the priming responses); P₁ and P₂, first and second cycles of priming stimulus; T refers to Triggering stimulus (Lethal/extreme stress to which priming promotes tolerance to); R refers to Recovery period (Phase between priming and triggering stress, at the optimum growth condition); d: days; h: hours; min: minutes; ABA, Abscisic acid; ADC, ARGININE DECARBOXYLASE; AKR, ALDO-KETO REDUCTASE; ALA, 5-aminolevulinic acid; *AOX1a*, *ALTERNATIVE OXIDASE 1A*; APX, ASCORBATE PEROXIDASE; *AREB3*, *ABA-RESPONSIVE ELEMENT BINDING PROTEIN 3*; ASM, Acibenzolar-S-methyl; BADH, BETAINE ALDEHYDE DEHYDROGENASE; BAP, Benzyl Aminopurine; BRU1, BRUSHY1; Ca, Calcium; CaCl₂, Calcium chloride; CAT, CATALASE; *CDPK3*, *CALCIUM-DEPENDENT PROTEIN KINASE 3*; Cl, Chloride; CPN60β, BETA-SUBUNIT OF CHAPERONIN-60; Cu, Copper; Cu NPs, Copper nanoparticles; DAO, DIAMINE OXIDASE; DHA, DEHYDROASCORBATE; DHAR, DEHYDROASCORBATE REDUCTASE; *DREB2A*, *DEHYDRATION-RESPONSIVE ELEMENT-BINDING PROTEIN 2A*; GB, Glycine betaine; Gly I, GLYOXALASE I; Gly II, GLYOXALASE II; GPX, GLUTATHIONE PEROXIDASE; GR, GLUTATHIONE REDUCTASE; GSH, Glutathione; GSSG, Glutathione disulfide; GST, GLUTATHIONE S-TRANSFERASE; H₂O₂, Hydrogen peroxide; *HSA32*, *HEAT STRESS-ASSOCIATED 32*; *HSFA2*, *HEAT SHOCK TRANSCRIPTION FACTOR A2*; HSP, HEAT SHOCK PROTEIN; IAA, Indole acetic acid; JA, Jasmonic acid; K, Potassium; KCZ, Ketoconazole; KM, Kresoxim-methyl; *MPK3*, *MITOGEN-ACTIVATED PROTEIN KINASE 3*; MDA, Malondialdehyde; Na, Sodium; NaCl, Sodium chloride; NaHS, Sodium hydrosulfide; NO, Nitric oxide; NOHS, Nitric oxide and Hydrogen sulfide; NR, NITRATE REDUCTASE; ODC, ORNITHINE DECARBOXYLASE; PAO, POLYAMINE OXIDASE; P5CS, Δ'-PYRROLINE-5-CARBOXYLATE SYNTHETASE; PEG, Poly(ethylene glycol); PH, Protein hydrolysates; POD, PEROXIDASE; POX, PROLINE OXIDASE; PPF, photosynthetic photon flux density; ppm, parts per million; PPO, POLYPHENOL OXIDASE; PR3, PATHOGENESIS RELATED PROTEIN 3; *psbA*, *photosystem II protein D1*; pTAC5, PLASTID TRANSCRIPTIONALLY ACTIVE CHROMOSOME 5; RCA1,

RUBISCO ACTIVASE 1; *RCD*, *RADICAL INDUCED CELL DEATH*; SA, Salicylic acid; SNP, Sodium nitroprusside; SOD, SUPEROXIDE DISMUTASE; *SOS1*, *SALT OVERLY SENSITIVE 1*; Spd, Spermidine; Spm, Spermine; RWC, relative water content; SRWC, soil relative water content; *ZAT*, *ZINC FINGER of Arabidopsis thaliana*; Zn, Zinc.

Supplemental References

- Antoniou, C., Xenofontos, R., Chatzimichail, G., Christou, A., Kashfi, K. and Fotopoulos, V.** 2020. Exploring the potential of nitric oxide and hydrogen sulfide (NOSH)-releasing synthetic compounds as novel priming agents against drought stress in *Medicago sativa* plants. *Biomolecules* **10**, 120.
- Ashraf, M.Y., Azhar, N. and Hussain, M.** 2006. Indole acetic acid (IAA) induced changes in growth, relative water contents and gas exchange attributes of barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) grown under water stress conditions. *Plant Growth Regulation* **50**, 85.
- Bajehbaj, A.A.** 2010. The effects of NaCl priming on salt tolerance in sunflower germination and seedling grown under salinity conditions. *African Journal of Biotechnology* **9**.
- Bajwa AA, Farooq M, Nawaz A.** 2018. Seed priming with sorghum extracts and benzyl aminopurine improves the tolerance against salt stress in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *Physiology and Molecular Biology of Plants* **24**, 239-249
- Brzezinka K, Altmann S, Bäurle I.** 2019. BRUSHY1/TONSOKU/MGOUN3 is required for heat stress memory. *Plant, cell & environment* **42**, 771–781.
- Buttar, Z. A, Wu, S. N, Arnao, M. B, Wang, C, Ullah, I, & Wang, C.** 2020. Melatonin suppressed the heat stress-induced damage in wheat seedlings by modulating the antioxidant machinery. *Plants*, **9(7)**, 809.
- Cao, Y.-Y. and Hua, Z.** 2008. Protective roles of brassinolide on rice seedlings under high temperature stress. *Rice Science* **15**, 63-68.
- Chattopadhyay, M.K, Tiwari, B.S, Chattopadhyay, G, Bose, A, Sengupta, D.N. and Ghosh, B.** 2002. Protective role of exogenous polyamines on salinity-stressed rice (*Oryza sativa*) plants. *Physiologia Plantarum* **116**, 192-199.
- Christou, A, Filippou, P., Manganaris, G. A., & Fotopoulos, V.** 2014. Sodium hydrosulfide induces systemic thermotolerance to strawberry plants through transcriptional regulation of heat shock proteins and aquaporin. *BMC plant biology*, **14(1)**, 1-11.
- El-Mashad, A.A.A. and Mohamed, H.I.** 2012. Brassinolide alleviates salt stress and increases antioxidant activity of cowpea plants (*Vigna sinensis*). *Protoplasma*, **249**, 625–635.
- Endres, L, Oliveira, N.G, Ferreira, V.M, and Silva, J.V.** 2016. Morphological and physiological response of sugarcane under abiotic stress to neonicotinoid insecticides. *Theoretical and Experimental Plant Physiology* **28**, 347–355.
- Fan, J., Xu, J., Zhang, W., Ameer, M., Liu, D., and Chen, L.** 2019. Salt-induced damage is alleviated by short-term pre-cold treatment in Bermudagrass (*Cynodon dactylon*). *Plants* **8(9)**, 347.
- Faralli, M., Lektemur, C., Rosellini, D. and Gürel, F.** 2015. Effects of heat shock and salinity on barley growth and stress-related gene transcription. *Biologia plantarum* **59**, 537-546.
- Filippou, P., Antoniou, C., Obata, T., Van Der Kelen, K., Harokopos, V., Kanetis, L., Aidinis, V., Van Breusegem, F., Fernie, A.R. and Fotopoulos, V.** 2016. Kresoxim-methyl primes *Medicago truncatula* plants against abiotic stress factors via altered reactive oxygen and nitrogen species signalling leading to downstream transcriptional and metabolic readjustment. *Journal of experimental botany* **67**, 1259-1274.

- Ford, K.A., Casida, J.E., Chandran, D., Gulevich, A.G., Okrent, R.A., Durkin, K.A., Sarpong, R., Bunnelle, E.M. and Wildermuth, M.C.** 2010. Neonicotinoid insecticides induce salicylate-associated plant defense responses. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* **107**, 17527-17532.
- Gohari, G., Alavi, Z., Esfandiari, E., Panahirad, S., Hajihoseinlou, S. and Fotopoulos, V.** 2020. Interaction between hydrogen peroxide and sodium nitroprusside following chemical priming of *Ocimum basilicum* L. against salt stress. *Physiologia plantarum* **168**, 361-373.
- Hameed, A., Farooq, T., Hameed, A., & Sheikh, M. A.** 2021. Sodium nitroprusside mediated priming memory invokes water-deficit stress acclimation in wheat plants through physio-biochemical alterations. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry*, **160**, 329-340.
- Hasanuzzaman, M., Alam, M., Rahman, A., Hasanuzzaman, M., Nahar, K. and Fujita, M.** 2014. Exogenous proline and glycine betaine mediated upregulation of antioxidant defense and glyoxalase systems provides better protection against salt-induced oxidative stress in two rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) varieties. *BioMed Research International* **757219**, 2014.
- Hossain, M.A., Mostofa, M.G. and Fujita, M.** 2013. Heat-shock positively modulates oxidative protection of salt and drought-stressed mustard (*Brassica campestris* L.) seedlings. *Journal of Plant Science and Molecular Breeding* **2**, 2.
- Irani, S., & Todd, C. D.** 2018. Exogenous allantoin increases Arabidopsis seedlings tolerance to NaCl stress and regulates expression of oxidative stress response genes. *Journal of plant physiology* **221**, 43-50.
- Jaleel, C. A., Lakshmanan, G. M. A., Gomathinayagam, M., & Panneerselvam, R.** 2008. Triadimefon induced salt stress tolerance in *Withania somnifera* and its relationship to antioxidant defense system. *South African Journal of Botany* **74**(1), 126-132.
- Jaleel, C. A., Manivannan, P., Sankar, B., Kishorekumar, A., Gopi, R., Somasundaram, R., & Panneerselvam, R.** 2007. Induction of drought stress tolerance by ketoconazole in *Catharanthus roseus* is mediated by enhanced antioxidant potentials and secondary metabolite accumulation. *Colloids and surfaces B: Biointerfaces*, **60**(2), 201-206.
- Jespersen, D., Yu, J. and Huang, B.** 2017. Metabolic effects of acibenzolar-S-methyl for improving heat or drought stress in creeping bentgrass. *Frontiers in plant science* **8**, 1224.
- Jiménez-Arias, D., Pérez, J.A., Luis, J.C., Martín-Rodríguez, V., Valdés-González, F., and Borges, A.A.** 2015. Treating seeds in menadione sodium bisulphite primes salt tolerance in Arabidopsis by inducing an earlier plant adaptation. *Environmental and experimental botany* **109**, 23–30.
- Kerchev, P., van der Meer, T., Sujeeth, N., Verlee, A., Stevens, C.V., Van Breusegem, F. and Gechev, T.** 2020. Molecular priming as an approach to induce tolerance against abiotic and oxidative stresses in crop plants. *Biotechnology Advances* **40**, 107503.
- Khan, A. and Ashraf, M.** 2008. Exogenously applied ascorbic acid alleviates salt-induced oxidative stress in wheat. *Environmental and experimental botany* **63**, 224-231.
- Korkmaz, A., Korkmaz, Y., & Demirkıran, A. R.** 2010. Enhancing chilling stress tolerance of pepper seedlings by exogenous application of 5-aminolevulinic acid. *Environmental and Experimental Botany* **67**(3), 495-501.
- Li, X., Topbjerg, H.B., Jiang, D. and Liu, F.** 2015. Drought priming at vegetative stage improves the antioxidant capacity and photosynthesis performance of wheat exposed to a short-term low temperature stress at jointing stage. *Plant and soil* **393**, 307-318.

- Li, Z. G., Yang, S. Z., Long, W. B., Yang, G. X., & Shen, Z. Z.** 2013. Hydrogen sulphide may be a novel downstream signal molecule in nitric oxide-induced heat tolerance of maize (*Zea mays* L.) seedlings. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, **36**(8), 1564-1572.
- Lin, K. H., Chiou, Y. K., Hwang, S. Y., Chen, L. F. O., & Lo, H. F.** 2008. Calcium chloride enhances the antioxidative system of sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas*) under flooding stress. *Annals of Applied Biology*, **152**(2), 157-168.
- Majláth, I., Éva, C., Tajti, J., Khalil, R., Elsayed, N., Darko, E., Szalai, G. and Janda, T.** 2020. Exogenous methylglyoxal enhances the reactive aldehyde detoxification capability and frost-hardiness of wheat. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry* **149**, 75-85.
- Malekzadeh, P., Khara, J. and Heydari, R.** 2014. Alleviating effects of exogenous Gamma-aminobutyric acid on tomato seedling under chilling stress. *Physiology and Molecular Biology of Plants* **20**, 133-137.
- Manaf, H.H.** 2016. Beneficial effects of exogenous selenium, glycine betaine and seaweed extract on salt stressed cowpea plant. *Annals of Agricultural Sciences* **61**, 41-48.
- Mei, Y.-q. and Song, S.-q.** 2010. Response to temperature stress of reactive oxygen species scavenging enzymes in the cross-tolerance of barley seed germination. *Journal of Zhejiang University SCIENCE B* **11**, 965-972.
- Mendanha, T., Rosenqvist, E., Hyldgaard, B. and Ottosen, C.-O.** 2018. Heat priming effects on anthesis heat stress in wheat cultivars (*Triticum aestivum* L.) with contrasting tolerance to heat stress. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry* **132**, 213-221.
- Nerson, H. and Govers, A.** 1986. Salt priming of muskmelon seeds for low-temperature germination. *Scientia Horticulturae* **28**, 85-91.
- Nounjan, N., Nghia, P.T., and Theerakulpisut, P.** 2012. Exogenous proline and trehalose promote recovery of rice seedlings from salt-stress and differentially modulate antioxidant enzymes and expression of related genes. *Journal of plant physiology*, **169**, 596–604.
- Pérez-Labrada, F., López-Vargas, E.R., Ortega-Ortiz, H., Cadenas-Pliego, G., Benavides-Mendoza, A. and Juárez-Maldonado, A.** 2019. Responses of tomato plants under saline stress to foliar application of copper nanoparticles. *Plants* **8**, 151.
- Plaza-Wüthrich, S., Blösch, R., Rindisbacher, A., Cannarozzi, G. and Tadele, Z.** 2016. Gibberellin deficiency confers both lodging and drought tolerance in small cereals. *Frontiers in plant science* **7**, 643.
- Prasad, T.K., Anderson, M.D., Martin, B.A. and Stewart, C.R.** 1994. Evidence for chilling-induced oxidative stress in maize seedlings and a regulatory role for hydrogen peroxide. *The Plant Cell* **6**, 65-74.
- Qiu, Z., Guo, J., Zhu, A., Zhang, L. and Zhang, M.** 2014. Exogenous jasmonic acid can enhance tolerance of wheat seedlings to salt stress. *Ecotoxicology and environmental safety* **104**, 202-208.
- Quinet, M., Ndayiragije, A., Lefevre, I., Lambillotte, B., Dupont-Gillain, C.C. and Lutts, S.** 2010. Putrescine differently influences the effect of salt stress on polyamine metabolism and ethylene synthesis in rice cultivars differing in salt resistance. *Journal of Experimental Botany* **61**, 2719-2733.
- Rajaei, P. and Mohamadi, N.** 2013. Effect of beta-aminobutyric acid (BABA) on enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants of *Brassica napus* L. under drought stress. *International Journal of Biosciences* **3**, 41-47.
- Sagervanshi A, Naeem A, Geilfus C-M, Kaiser H, Mühlhng KH.** 2021. One-time abscisic acid priming induces long-term salinity resistance in *Vicia faba*: Changes in key transcripts, metabolites, and ionic relations. *Physiologia plantarum* **172**, 146–161.

- Stamm, M.D., Enders, L.S., Donze-Reiner, T.J., Baxendale, F.P., Siegfried, B.D., and Heng-Moss, T.M.** 2014. Transcriptional response of soybean to thiamethoxam seed treatment in the presence and absence of drought stress. *BMC Genomics*, **15**, 1055.
- Sorrentino, M., De Diego, N., Ugena, L., Spíchal, L., Lucini, L., Miras-Moreno, B., et al.** 2021. Seed Priming with protein hydrolysates improves Arabidopsis growth and stress tolerance to abiotic stresses. *Frontiers in plant science*, **12**, 626301.
- Sun, L., Li, X., Wang, Z., Sun, Z., Zhu, X., Liu, S., Song, F., Liu, F. and Wang, Y.** 2018. Cold priming induced tolerance to subsequent low temperature stress is enhanced by melatonin application during recovery in wheat. *Molecules* **23**, 1091.
- Tabassum, T., Farooq, M., Ahmad, R., Zohaib, A. and Wahid, A.** 2017. Seed priming and transgenerational drought memory improves tolerance against salt stress in bread wheat. *Plant Physiology and Biochemistry* **118**, 362-369.
- Uchida, A., Jagendorf, A.T., Hibino, T., Takabe, T. and Takabe, T.** 2002. Effects of hydrogen peroxide and nitric oxide on both salt and heat stress tolerance in rice. *Plant Science* **163**, 515-523.
- Wang, W., Wang, X., Zhang, J., Huang, M., Cai, J., Zhou, Q., Dai, T. and Jiang, D.** 2020. Salicylic acid and cold priming induce late-spring freezing tolerance by maintaining cellular redox homeostasis and protecting photosynthetic apparatus in wheat. *Plant Growth Regulation* **90**, 109-121.
- Wang, X., Vignjevic, M., Liu, F., Jacobsen, S., Jiang, D. and Wollenweber, B.** 2015. Drought priming at vegetative growth stages improves tolerance to drought and heat stresses occurring during grain filling in spring wheat. *Plant Growth Regulation* **75**, 677-687.
- Wang, X., Zhang, X., Chen, J., Wang, X., Cai, J., Zhou, Q., Dai, T., Cao, W. and Jiang, D.** 2018. Parental drought-priming enhances tolerance to post-anthesis drought in offspring of wheat. *Frontiers in plant science* **9**, 261.
- Wang X, Li Z, Liu B, Zhou H, Elmongy MS, Xia Y.** 2020. Combined proteome and transcriptome analysis of heat-primed Azalea reveals new insights into plant heat acclimation memory. *Frontiers in plant science* **11**, 1278.
- Wang X, Chen J, Ge J, Huang M, Cai J, Zhou Q, Dai T, Mur LAJ, Jiang D.** 2021. The different root apex zones contribute to drought priming induced tolerance to a reoccurring drought stress in wheat. *The Crop Journal* **9**, 1088–1097.
- Wang, Y., Zhang, H., Hou, P., Su, X., Zhao, P., Zhao, H. and Liu, S.** 2014. Foliar-applied salicylic acid alleviates heat and high light stress induced photoinhibition in wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) during the grain filling stage by modulating the psbA gene transcription and antioxidant defense. *Plant growth regulation* **73**, 289-297.
- Xing, W. and Rajashekar, C.** 2001. Glycine betaine involvement in freezing tolerance and water stress in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *Environmental and Experimental Botany* **46**, 21-28.
- Yamamoto, C.J.T., Leite, R.G.F., Minamiguchi, J.Y., Braga, I., Neto, N.B.M. and Custódio, C.C.** 2014. Water-deficit tolerance induction during germination of Jalo Precoce bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) cultivar. *Acta physiologiae plantarum* **36**, 2897-2904.
- Yan, Z., Ming, D., CUI, J.-x., CHEN, X.j., WEN, Z.l., ZHANG, J.w. and LIU, H.y.** 2018. Exogenous GSH protects tomatoes against salt stress by modulating photosystem II efficiency, absorbed light allocation and H₂O₂-scavenging system in chloroplasts. *Journal of Integrative Agriculture* **17**, 2257-2272.
- Yang, X., Xu, H., Li, D., Gao, X., Li, T. and Wang, R.** 2018. Effect of melatonin priming on photosynthetic capacity of tomato leaves under low-temperature stress. *Photosynthetica* **56**, 884-892.

- Yu, R., Zuo, T., Diao, P., et al.** 2021. Melatonin enhances seed germination and seedling growth of *Medicago sativa* under salinity via a putative melatonin receptor MsPMTR1. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, **12**.
- Zhang, H., Jiao, H., Jiang, C.-X., Wang, S.-H., Wei, Z.-J., Luo, J.-P. and Jones, R.L.** 2010. Hydrogen sulfide protects soybean seedlings against drought-induced oxidative stress. *Acta physiologiae plantarum* **32**, 849-857.
- Zhang, X., Wang, X., Zhuang, L., Gao, Y. and Huang, B.** 2019. Abscisic acid mediation of drought priming-enhanced heat tolerance in tall fescue (*Festuca arundinacea*) and Arabidopsis. *Physiologia Plantarum* **167**, 488-501.
- Zhao, M.-G., Chen, L., Zhang, L.-L. and Zhang, W.-H.** 2009. Nitric reductase-dependent nitric oxide production is involved in cold acclimation and freezing tolerance in Arabidopsis. *Plant physiology* **151**, 755-767.